

**FORMATIVE AND SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT
IN HIGHER EDUCATION:
OPINIONS AND PRACTICES OF INSTRUCTORSⁱ**

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to examine opinions of the instructors working in three different universities in Ankara regarding assessment in education and assessment methods they use in their courses within the summative assessment and formative assessment approaches. The population is formed by instructors lecturing in School of Physical Education and Sport and Sports Sciences Faculties of three universities (Ankara, Gazi and Hacettepe Universities) located in Ankara in quantitative section of the survey. Its sample is formed of 61 instructors taking part in quantitative section and 27 instructors taking part in qualitative section. The research is a mixed research design including both quantitative and qualitative survey model. A questionnaire form, composed of three sections and developed by the researchers, has been used for qualitative data collection tool in the survey. As quantitative data collection tool, "semi-structured personal interviews" have been conducted. Descriptive statistics is used in the survey for qualitative results in analysis of data and results have been evaluated with frequencies, percentages and means in the tables. And for the quantitative survey, content analysis method has been used for the assessment of the interviews. It is identified according to the results of the survey that the participation percentage of the instructors to the opinions towards the inquiry questions related to assessment were high ($\bar{X}=4,48\pm0,34$). It is determined that the methods most used by the instructors in applied courses are; skill tests (f: 26), performance assessment (f:19) and project (f:10)

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while in theoretical courses “multiple choice tests” (f: 39), “open ended questions” (f: 35) and “true-false questions” (f:28) were the methods used at most. In the result of qualitative data analysis of the survey, opinions of the instructors regarding assessment are assessed under formative and summative assessment categories. When we examined the opinions of the instructors related to the importance of assessment in education, it is concluded that the formative assessment characteristics as increasing motivation, self-assessment of the instructor, providing a chance to re-arrange the instruction process via feedback have been placed at the top of the list; however, in the implementation the assessments have been made by summative assessment methods rather than formative assessment methods.

Keywords: assessment, formative assessment, summative assessment, instructors, higher education

1. Introduction

Assessment system is a very important feature in determining the behavior and attitude of the student regarding learning (Freeman, 1995), in determining the decisions of the instructor before education, during education and after education (McMillan, 2014, p. 11), and in ensuring the control of the education activities (Tan, 2012). Assessment is defined as the most effective feature on the learning of the student (Gibbs, & Simpson, 2004). When considered from the perspective of the student, according to Biggs (1996), assessment method increases the effort of the students regarding the student’s studies and learning. However, according to Palmer (2004), assessment method selected by the instructor affects learning habits of the student. When importance of assessment is observed in terms of the instructor, pre-assessment made by the instructor (descriptive), formative assessment made during the lecture, and summative (final) assessment made after the lecture affect the decisions of the instructor about the course. At this point, achieving an assessment in three stages shall affect the appropriateness of the decisions given. Assessment is the determinant in all decisions to be taken by the instructor (Mc Millan, 2014, p. 13). Finally, when the education is considered as a systematic approach, like any other system, it is composed for input, process, output and assessment (control) features. Assessment also has an important role in ensuring control in every stage of education activities (Baykul, 1992). In order to increase the contribution of assessment, which is one of the most important elements of education-training process, researchers indicate that the transition to assessment for learning from assessment of learning is needed (Torrance, 2007). Within this context, qualified education ensures qualified

learning and qualified education is only possible via regular and qualified assessment (Nartgün, 2009). In order to facilitate qualitative assessment specified herein, more proper and comprehensive assessment tools should be used based on the structural harmony of the learning and the instructor (Biggs, 1996). This constructivist standing is generally stated as assessment for learning (Sambell, McDowell, & Montgomery, 2013). The tools developed to facilitate assessment are stated as traditional and alternative assessment tools and those tools are used in three stages of assessment. Having the assessment at the beginning of education process assists determining competencies of the students and planning education; having the assessment during the process facilitates the identification of defective points while the assessments made after the process assists to understand whether the educational services are adequate to meet the needs according to the results obtained.

Although assessment is very important for ensuring the sustainability of the education process healthily, it is an area generally neglected, of which importance is not attributed sufficiently, and summative assessment is very common. Even though lecturing and learning process needs to be an integrated pattern as a whole, especially in the higher education they are considered as separate areas (Offerdahl, & Tomanek, 2011). Assessment is often made to measure its effectiveness after the program; curriculum and content of the course are prepared. It is rarely observed that assessment is used to measure personal success or define learning of the student (William, Lee, Harrison, & Black, 2004). Higher education stage is the place where students are transferred to stage of producing information rather than providing them education (Barr, & Tagg, 1995). Within this context, higher education is the stage where the transition from assessment of learning needs to change into assessment for learning needs to be made. Without a doubt, the instructors at higher education play important roles in the transition stage. Newly developed education strategies focused on students requires the use of new methods to evaluate the learning of the student as well. Within this consideration, it is important that the instructors find new methods to collect new data regarding realization status within this changing process and providing harmonization to alternative assessment methods. In determination of the assessment method the instructor choose, it is important to examine the complex relation between the idea and practice. When the literature is searched, there are only a few studies putting forward the perspective and perception of the lecturers against assessment. Among those studies, Taras and Davies (2013) researched perceptions of the instructors related to the duties and processes of the assessment as well as realities; and they have found out that the assessment was an expertise yet is was placed in the center of the education in reality. In another study, instructors' new education strategies as well as

the opinions of three instructors on assessment have been defined by Offerdahl and Tomanek (2011), and it was observed that after practise process of alternative assessment strategies lasted for two periods, the opinions of instructors regarding assessment had been more comprehensive and they had the tendency to have more formative assessment. In another study, Liu and Li (2014) applied assessment training exercises to the students, and as a result they have found out that there was a significant decrease between the assessment of the instructor and students at the end of the training. Nartgün (2009) conducted a study, where instructors' assessments were evaluated according to the students throughout education, the researcher concluded that majority of instructors did not complete their tasks related to assessment successfully throughout the education or at the beginning of the education, and assessment based on performance was not executed by majority of instructors.

Assessment in the higher education, which is one of the most important levels in the education process, plays an important role both for providing the student a more qualified education and ensuring the student as a more competent person after graduation. In executing the assessments with this intention, the perspectives of the instructors towards assessment and the assessment methods they use play a definitive role. Within the context of the provided data, the purpose of this study is to examine the opinions of instructors in assessment in education and the assessment methods they use within the framework learning of assessment and understanding in assessment for learning. With this purpose, answers to the following questions listed below are sought:

1. What are the opinions of the instructors related to assessment?
2. What are the methods used by instructors when they are assessing the students?
3. What are the opinions of instructors towards assessment within the framework of formative assessment and summative assessment?

1.1 Summative assessment (Assessment of learning)

Summative assessment, stated as the assessment of learning, is an assessment method used for the purpose of certifying learning, submitting reports to the students and their families about the development of the students, and giving signs to the students about their own positions comparing themselves with other students (Earl, 2004, p. 22). It can be told that the use of traditional assessment types those have very important results for the participant may have some negative effects in terms of pedagogy. First of all, result oriented education system only focuses the students to get higher exam results and instructors may face a process of education for exams with this perspective (Williams, 2014). Second negative side limits the usage percentage of feedbacks and it causes lack of learning cycle in the self-assessment point of the student (Williams, 2014).

Nevertheless, well-designed constructivist feedbacks have a very important motivational value that increases the level of learning (Black, & Wiliam, 1998; Taras 2002; Brennan, & Williams, 2004).

1.2 Formative assessment (Assessment for learning)

Formative assessment is a type of assessment that covers collecting proof about learning of the student, providing feedback to the students and practical education strategies to improve success; and realizing those by using alternative assessment tool throughout education process (McMillan, 2014, p.111). Assessment for learning means transition from summative assessment to formative assessment. When assessment for learning is executed the people specified as instructor collect various data to arrange learning studies of students (Earl, 2004, p.24). In other words, formative assessment shapes the education. Formative assessment ensures to address the learner during education life and facilitates guidance (Rodrigues & Oliveira, 2014). The purpose is to increase learning and motivation. According to Sadler (1987) the core of formative learning is to define the gap between the real performance and desired performance (as cited in Lipnevick, McCallen, Miles & Smith, 2014). Although many studies have been conducted on formative assessment lately and very important recommendations have been given, formative assessment is not used sufficiently (Sinclair, & Cleland, 2007).

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Research model

Mixed research design has been used in the research. Within this context, both qualitative and quantitative methods have been benefited. Mixed design is defined as a research giving opportunity to data collection, analyzing and integration via qualitative and quantitative design (Yıldırım, & Şimşek, 2013). In the research, quantitative data have been used for giving a general idea related to the perspective of the instructors towards assessment and for identifying the ratio of the used assessment methods. Qualitative data are used for deeply examining the opinion of the instructors towards assessment.

2.2 Participants

In qualitative section of the research (n=61), and 27 instructors participated in the quantitative section of the research voluntarily. The research has been conducted in 2013-2014 education year in Ankara, Turkey. While sample is chosen for the research, criterion sampling has been conducted among sampling methods with purpose and

instructors of sciences in sports, who work in three universities and who can open and give lectures on their names, have been selected for the research. Other than this one, in the selection of the schools modal sampling that is easy to access is used. Selected three universities are located in the cities the researchers reside and they are in an accessible distance both in the qualitative and quantitative data collection.

The breakdown of instructors, who participated in the quantitative section of the research, by universities, seniority, and their titles is given in table 1.

Table 1: Data related to the Instructors

		f	%	
Instructor	Seniority	0-10	9	14.1
		11-20	20	33.3
		21 - 30	22	36.8
		31 and more	10	15.8
		Total	61	100
	Title	Professor	11	17,5
		Associate Professor	14	22,8
		Assistant Professor	17	28,1
		Lecturer	19	31,6
	Total	61	100,0	
	University	Ankara University	19	32
		Gazi University	26	40
Hacettepe University		16	28	
Total		61	100	

2.3 Data collection

As data collection tool, a questionnaire form composed of three sections and a semi-structured questionnaire form have been created by the researchers. The questionnaire form and interview questions have been formed by establishing a pool of questions from the studies conducted in this topic and taking the opinions of the experts. The first section of the questionnaire form is composed of personal information. The second part is formed of 13 questions of 5 point likert scale composed of requirements of the formative assessment in education. The third section is composed of the section we want the instructors to write down the three methods they use mostly in theoretical and applied courses. About the second part of the questionnaire, the related Cronbach Alpha value is identified to be 0.81. The purpose of the research has been explained to the instructors taking part in the survey and it was emphasized that the participation was completely voluntarily. When the filled questionnaire forms were collected, information was given about the qualitative section and interviews have been made with 27 instructors, who have accepted to meet by asking for their time to have the interview. Questions have been asked about importance of measurement-assessment,

its contribution to education, difficulties faced during practices, alternative assessment methods used in courses and their reflections to the courses in the semi-structured questionnaire forms that will assist them in assessments about the related topics. By interviewing with instructors working in different universities, in different titles and seniorities, diversification in data sources has been ensured. Voice recording has been used during the negotiations and the interviews lasted between 15 minutes to 45 minutes. Validity is the most important standard that indicates the quality of quantitative research process (Baden, & Major, 2013). In order to ensure validity of the survey, data collection focused on depth and comprehensive description techniques are used. Data collection focused on depth continuously compares the results achieved to each other, evaluated them conceptualized them bringing some patterns into the light of which people were not aware (Yıldırım, & Şimşek, 2013). Data collected for the security of quantitative data have been provided directly, associates also took part in the research, and help from different researchers were taken in analysis stage of the data (Yıldırım, & Şimşek, 2013).

2.4 Analysis of data

In the research descriptive statistics have been used in the analysis of qualitative data, and the results have been evaluated in frequencies, percentages and means in the tables. However, in the analysis of quantitative data, content analysis method has been used, interviews made with 27 instructors have been first coded separately by researchers and then they have been evaluated under themes specified in two different categories.

2.4.1 Data coding

After reading the interview data line by line, the codes, evaluated to be important by the researcher, have been underlined.

2.4.2 Finding the themes

When coding is completed, he related codes will be grouped and proper themes have been established. Thematic coding means categorizing already determined codes identifying their common sides.

3. Results

Firstly the opinions on the questionnaire and used the assessment instrument used are given in the quantitative dimension. Then the opinions parallel or contradictory to quantitative data were examined in depth.

3.1 Opinions of instructors about assessment and assessment tools used by instructors

Opinions of instructors in the assessment for learning within the research are provided in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Values related to opinions of instructors about assessment in education-teaching

	N	$\bar{X}$	Sd
Assessment must be a part of education-teaching process.	61	4,64	,55
The most proper method must be selected according to the specifications of the course.	61	4,68	,46
The assessment method I use must be appropriate for multi-way assessment of the success of the students.	61	4,73	,48
New and different methods related to assessment are often used in the courses.	61	4,31	,75
Adequate/sufficient time must be used to assess the students.	61	4,66	,51
Made assessments must give explanatory info on the performance of the student.	61	4,61	,52
The environment, where the measurement is made, must be considered to assess the success of the student.	61	4,50	,68
There must be different approaches other than perfect academic success in the assessment of the success.	61	4,33	,69
New assessment methods must be sought in order to assess students effectively and they must be tried to be practised.	61	4,26	,74
In physical education and sports areas new studies related to assessment must be followed closely.	61	4,49	,68
Performance of the student must be monitored continuously.	61	4,31	,60
Group assessment must be conducted as well as individual assessments.	61	3,98	,91
When assessments are made about the course, education process must be also added to the assessment.	61	4,43	,62
General	61	4,48	,34

Questionnaire: 1=I do not agree at all 2= I do not agree, 3=Indecisive, 4= I agree, 5=I totally agree

It is observed that according to the questionnaire results, the instructors totally agree with the opinions about the assessment and the mean of the opinions are quite high ($\bar{X}=4.48\pm 0.34$). The opinion they most agree is "The assessment method I use must be appropriate for multi-way assessment of the success of the students" ($\bar{X}:4.73 \pm 0.48$), and the opinion they least agree is "Group assessment must be conducted as well as individual assessments" ($\bar{X}:3.98 \pm 0.91$).

Table 3. The methods instructors use at most in theoretical courses

	f	%
	39	38,2
The 3 methods used at most	Multiple choice tests	
	Open ended questions	35 34,3
	True-False questions	28 27,5
Total	102	100,0

It is observed as a result of the research that the assessment methods used at most in theoretical courses are multiple choice tests (f:39), open ended questions (f:35) and True/False questions (f:28).

Table 4. The methods instructors use in applied courses at most

	f	%
	27	48,21
The 3 methods used at most	Skill tests	
	Performance assessment	19 33,92
	Project	10 17,85
Total	56	100,0

It is observed as a result of the research that the assessment methods used at most in applied courses are skill tests (f:27), performance assessment (f:19) and project (f:10). Despite the high average of opinions on assessment in education the most commonly used assessment tools mostly in theoretical courses are suitable for summative assessment. In order to more deeply understand their views on assessment qualitative findings are presented under the categories of summative assessment and formative assessment.

3.2 Summative assessment (Assessment of learning)

Opinions of instructors related to summative assessment, stated as assessment of learning, have been interpreted under the themes, its importance, difficulties faced and effective methods.

3.2.1 Importance

Summative assessment is executed for determining the success of the group, listing, and submitting reports when the learning tasks are completed. At this point, it is observed that perspective of some of the instructors towards assessment is formed within this context.

“It is important for listing the currently available situation of individuals. We cannot make an objective classification between the groups if we do not make measurement-assessment, and among the individuals within the group.”

(Instructor-12)

“Putting forward what is currently available and reaching a solution with the data at the same time...”

(Instructor-16)

“It is important for understanding the level which students fulfill the targets of the course. We seek for the answers to the question “how much.”

(Instructor-23)

“Measures, scores, notes we obtain as a result of the measurement-assessment provide us a feedback and if we obtain high scores herein, it means we have already achieved what we desire in learning...”

(Instructor-20)

3.2.2 Difficulties faced

It is observed that in the methods used by instructors in summative assessment, habits of the students, insufficient time, the exam type not being able to separate the successful one from the unsuccessful one, crowded classes and alike are the difficulties faced.

“Students got used to see a different method that they feel awkward for the method I use. There is only one mid-term at the universities; however, the instructor may give more exams. That is what I do. They are not used to have more than one exam. They feel like just have one and I will get prepared for that and it will be finished. Actually, repeating a couple of times ensures the learning and the student has more chances. Yet, the student interprets differently and objects.”

(Instructor-3)

“If you are going to make assessment in applied courses, you follow general exercises due to time restrictions. Since you do not have time, you cannot assess them in couples; we cannot use different methods, either. In usual courses, if you want to make presentations you need to zip them again due to time restrictions.”

(Instructor-10)

"...It is seen that classically exams are made in the way students get used to. This causes the issue to be evaluated as a whole. You ask three of four questions and those students who may know the three or four questions get better scores. However, a student better than the one who answered those questions cannot be able to answer the questions. The people, who make the assessment, need to ask questions addressed to the entire unit/audience and they need to ask questions by diversifying them..."

(Instructor-14)

"Number of students... The best measurement-assessment is made mutually and when completed by observation. When you have huge numbers of students, it is obligatory to use mechanical methods. Those methods never give the real result..."

(Instructor-27)

3.2.3 Effective methods

It is taking attentions that the high number of the instructors, who believe that the tools used in the summative assessment among the used assessment methods are more effective. In terms of need for conducting analysis to indicate whether the answer is really known open ended questions are the ones used very often and in order to ensure objectivity multiple choice tests are the methods used at most and it is stated by the instructors that those are thought to be effective methods.

"I mostly use questions with long answers open for interpretation. I believe that is most correct method."

(Instructor-9)

"I believe questions with short answers are more effective. The possibility to take the chance or see the answers of the student nearby is high in multiple choice tests. In long answered questions they write to long even though they do not know the answer."

(Instructor-10)

"Always an essay test. I keep the classical questions with long answers in the first place. I also find mixed tests developed according to that course valuable. Also, I believe that oral exams are very important."

(Instructor-12)

"I believe the most effective ones are the inquiries made in analytical level; that means open ended questions. I usually ask them in final exams. However, in the mid-term

exams I usually ask question-answer and multiple choice tests those take information directly."

(Instructor-13)

"Exams with long answers because in such exams you find out if the students really know the answer or not..."

(Instructor-20)

Another reason why instructors believe multiple choice exams are more effective is the students are used to have that assessment method and they prefer it. For example;

"Multiple choice exams are internalized from the perspective of students. I observe that they avoid questions with long answers. They prefer multiple choice tests. We try to prevent them from cheating by grouping single type questions. Since the exams are based on multiple choice tests today, I believe it is appropriate to have a pattern they may use in their lives."

(Instructor-15)

3.3 Formative assessment (Assessment for learning)

Opinions of instructors those include classification of formative assessment are interpreted under themes of motivation, self-assessment, regulating education, difficulties faced and effective methods.

3.3.1 Motivation

One of the important contributions of formative assessment, stated as assessment as learning, is ensuring immediate feedback and increasing motivation since it fulfills the needs. When we considered the opinions of the instructors related to assessment, we observe that they attribute importance to the assessment due to this specification.

"First of all, it has an importance to ensure better motivation of the student and to understand whether the student learned or not...I feel like measurement-assessment is also a learning process..."

(Instructor-10)

"If we make an objective assessment, this both increases the motivation of the student and the deficiencies are better detected as an instructor and studies for abolishing deficiencies may be conducted."

(Instructor-18)

3.3.2 Self-assessment

Another characteristic of formative assessment is it provides opportunity to assess the performance of both the student and the instructor's own performance. This characteristic indicates that formative assessment encourages self-assessment. According to instructors, those characteristics make the assessment important.

"You also assess yourself. It will give you a path to increase your own education quality"

(Instructor-8)

"It is important in terms of how students react in which period and understanding how much students understood as well as understanding our own mistake."

(Instructor-4)

"It is important in terms of assessing yourself on your own because usually measurement-assessment group gives you the chance to assess the instructor himself other than assessment...."

(Instructor-25)

"Nevertheless, it is first of all important to inquire the person giving the lecture himself personally. How much can I transfer, I am sufficient? This is very important. Different instructors give the same courses. Everything is the same but the result may differ. It is important to bring those out. ..."

(Instructor-21)

3.3.3 Regulating education

One of the important features of formative assessment is ensuring reviewing education according to the feedback received. With this qualification, the instructor rearranges the content of the education, teaching method used, and the material in order to reach the desired target. Opinions of the instructor at this point indicate that they take formative assessment as more importantly.

“Again, according to the feedback you receive, it is classically important to see why the student could not learn instead of whether the student learnt or not in your good and bad practices. In order to see if the used teaching method is correct this is important. The quality of education will increase parallel to that.”

(Instructor-5)

“...If there is gain, it is a must to have measurement-assessment...If the kid could not take what s/he needs to have, then there is either a problem in the method or the program is not proper to the kid. This only provides is what they did not have only for increasing the quality. Thus, this is the first step to make the plan of the following lecture.”

(Instructor-7)

“Right after the measurement-assessment we need to identify the deficiencies with accurate analysis, where did we make mistakes, did we able to put a correct method forward? Which method brought to which point? Would another method be more useful? It is important to find answers to these questions....”

(Instructor-14)

“There are two important things in measurement-assessment. One of them is the assessment of the students. The second one is if the problem does not come from the student’s side, and then there may be a problem in the planning. This result we have should be corrected on which issue it is and thus, in order to solve the problem assessment is very important...”

(Instructor-15)

3.3.4 Difficulties faced

Although there are studies conducted about importance of formative assessment and recommendations are available, there is no tradition of formative assessment in higher education neither in terms of student nor instructor. At this point, perspective of the students through alternative assessment methods and preparedness level are important. At this point, the level of the students are one of the difficulties faced according to the instructors.

“I am trying to use assessment methods focusing students; however, lack of students’ required level in this issue or the fact that they are not aware is pushing us to use instructor focused methods. I want to assess the result and the process. I want them to

make performance and colleague assessment yet they are doing it unaware of its importance. Then, I believe that the assessments are left insufficient."

(Instructor-23)

"For example, I assign them project work. They bring me 5 to 10 pages. But our course is an applied course and I want to see a visual video rather than that. I experienced that it was more useful when applied."

(Instructor-2)

3.3.5 Effective methods

When the opinions of instructors are examined in terms of the methods used in applied courses, we observe that some of the instructors use alternative assessment approaches that may be used with the purpose of formative assessment (self-assessment, colleague assessment, portfolio, observation forms) in their courses and efficiency has been achieved.

"It is important for them to make self-assessment, and also it is important for them to assess the others, product folder"

(Instructor-4)

"...I believe that the most effective method is the observation. The best way to understand how much the student understands and how s/he understands is to observe what the student does. I want to have them repeat the previous hour in my courses. If the student cannot do that then s/he cannot learn that. We do not need an extra method to see that."

(Instructor-27)

"For example, after showing then body elements of modern dance and tell them what they are going to use, I want them to see at least two modern dance shows in this term and criticize the shows. Maybe they will do what they will never do and they watch the show twice and compare."

(Instructor-3)

"...When you assign a student a project, s/he searches a different topic and sometimes that topic may be within his/her intention and they like the course more than usual. I have simple weekly homework."

(Instructor-10)

4. Discussion and Conclusion

When results of quantitative method is examined, it is identified that the participation level was high among instructors indicating they “totally agree” with the opinions regarding measurement-assessment ($\bar{X}$: 4,48±0,34). It is observed as a result of the research that the assessment methods used at most in theoretical courses are multiple choice tests (f:39), open ended questions (f:35) and True/False questions (f:28). The assessment methods used at most in applied courses are aptitude tests (f: 27), performance assessment (f: 19) and project (f:10). Bay and colleagues (2010) in a survey conducted with 75 instructors and 274 candidates of instructors, it was found out that traditional measurement-assessment tools were used more than alternative tools; however, opinions regarding use of alternative assessment methods were affirmative. Considering the mostly used measurement tools in our survey, we can say that it reaches parallel results with the research conducted by Bay and colleagues (2010). In the study, where Şad and Göktaş (2013) examine opinions of instructors towards traditional and authentic assessment approaches, it was found out that the approaches for traditional and authentic assessment were favored in average level. Although the high value we have obtained in our survey regarding measurement-assessment ($\bar{X}$: 4,48±0,34) does not match with the findings of Şad and Göktaş (2013), the very often use of traditional tools in terms of measurement can be interpreted as the alternative assessment has not been accepted adequately. Arslantaş (2011) identified that instructors were not in sufficient level in the study he evaluated the ability to use strategy methods and techniques of instructors as well as their ability to communicate and measurement-assessment. In the study of Aksu, Çivitçi and Duy (2008), where opinions of students of higher education were examined towards the behaviors of instructors within the class, course practices, and measurement-assessment practices, it was concluded that students of higher education had negative perceptions in measurement-assessment practices of instructors Those results achieved from the survey of Arslantaş (2011) and Aksu and colleagues (2008), are important since they support the difference between the opinions and practices of the instructors. In the study we have evaluated the opinions of instructors about assessment and the methods they use within the framework of formative and summative assessment, it is observed that the opinions of instructors about assessment are closer to the purposes of formative assessment. Identification of deficiencies during the process, instructors giving opportunities to themselves for self-evaluation, increasing motivation, re-planning the education according to the deficiencies identified, and similar opinions reflecting the purposes of formative assessments are specified by the instructors. In terms of the use

of evaluation according to the purpose of the assessment, it is found out both from the tools mostly used in assessment tools in quantitative section and interviews that it was commonly applied as summative assessment method. At this point, while questions with open ended answers and multiple choice tests are among the most common methods used, it was identified that only a few instructors used measurement tools that may be used in formative assessment as observation, product folder and self-assessment. With this result, it is possible to say that the relation between the opinion and practice are not going parallel to each other. IT is important to examine the complex relation between the opinion and the practice in determination of the method selected by instructor. When the literature is searched, there are only a few studies putting the perspective and perceptions of the instructors towards assessment. Among those studies, the study conducted by Taras and Davies (2013), the perceptions and realities of instructors related to the duties and processes of assessment have been researched, and they have identified that assessment has been perceived as an expertise by instructors but in reality it was located in the center of education. In another research, Offerdahl and Tomanek (2011) examined the opinions of instructors towards new education strategies along with assessment and within the scope of this study, opinions of three instructors regarding assessment have been defined and complex relation between the opinion and practise is examined encouraging the experiments of alternative assessment strategies. At the end of the experience of two terms, it was observed that the opinions of the instructors regarding assessment were more multi-dimensional and their opinions changed into less summative assessment and more formative assessment (Tomanek, 2011). In Nartgün (2009)'s study, where assessment practices of instructors were assessed according to the students during the education, it was observed that majority of instructors did not complete their duties regarding assessment successfully throughout the education or at the beginning of the education; and it was observed that most of the instructors did not fulfill performance based assessments. The higher education, which is one of the most important levels of the individual, assessment is very important both having a more qualified education for the individual and to be a more competent person for the public after graduation. In the assessment executed with this understanding by the instructors, the importance attributed to assessment by the instructors and the assessment methods they use play definitive roles. The results give us that the opinions were mainly had formative characteristics while at the practise point, assessment tools mainly had summative characteristics. At this point, it will be very important to educate instructors on the purpose of formative assessment and the most effective alternative assessment tools as well as increasing the similarity between the thoughts and practices.

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